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A Risk Assessment Method Using Neutrosophic PERT-FMEA

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ABSTRACT

Classical failure mode and effect analysis (FMEA) is a widely used technique for conducting risk analysis and evaluation in safety engineering. Nonetheless, it faces challenges because of its assumption of equal importance for severity, occurrence, and detection as well as uncertainties stemming from expert judgment and limited system data. To address these issues, this study introduces an FMEA extension utilizing the neutrosophic program evaluation and review technique (NPERT) approach. Furthermore, the significance weights of the risk parameters were established using the analytic hierarchy process (AHP) method, which is based on single-valued neutrosophic sets (SVNS) and triangular fuzzy numbers (TFNs). This method was hypothetically applied to a centrally controlled natural-gas heating system. Compared to the traditional FMEA, the proposed method produced more precise results and improved performance, facilitating better decision-making under uncertain conditions.

1 INTRODUCTION

The FMEA method has a wide range of applications; however, certain aspects require further development, particularly regarding applicability, cause-and-effect relationships, risk analysis, and problem solving [1]. Key problems that researchers have focused on within the scope of applicability include the diverse expertise areas of decision-makers, epistemic uncertainties arising from varying experience levels, difficulties experts face in precisely assessing the severity of risk factors, and potential biases in FMEA results [2, 3, 4]. Another commonly criticized issue is the assumption that all risk factors are equally weighted [5]. To address these issues, numerous researchers have sought to enhance the performance of the FMEA method by applying fuzzy logic and multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) techniques. Mete [6] proposed integrating AHP and MOORA (multi-objective optimization on the basis of ratio analysis) techniques based on pythagorean fuzzy logic into the FMEA method to assess occupational risks in a natural gas pipeline project, achieving successful results. Cai et al. [2] proposed extending the traditional FMEA method using bayesian networks and extended dempster's rules to improve its performance. Their study demonstrated that this approach effectively addresses epistemic uncertainty arising from expert judgments and produces more objective results. In their study, Safari et al. [7] developed an FMEA method based on the fuzzy-VIKOR (vlsekriterijumska optimizacija i kompromisno resenje) approach, which incorporates decision-maker weights and allows the evaluation of risk factors using linguistic variables. Testik and

Unlu [8] demonstrated that evaluations by decision-makers using fuzzy logic-based linguistic variables yield reliable results in FMEA applications. In their study, Kumari et al. [9] used the fuzzy analytical hierarchy process (FAHP) to weight FMEA risk factors and applied an FMEA method based on Fuzzy-VIKOR to rank the identified risks. In their study, Klarić et al. [10] proposed a novel methodology by integrating FAHP, fuzzy-TOPSIS (technique for the order of preference by similarity to ideal solution), and fuzzy-WINGS (weighted influence non-linear gauge system) methods into the FMEA framework, considering the complex interactions among failure modes. In the literature, studies addressing uncertainty and conflict in FMEA applications have utilized interval type-2 fuzzy sets (IT2FS), an enhanced form of fuzzy sets. Kan et al. [11] proposed an FMEA method based on gray relational projection (GRP)-VIKOR that employs IT2FS to assess risks threatening the safety of submarine pipelines. Azadi et al. [12] aimed to improve customer relationship management by weighting identified risk factors using IT2FS-AHP and ranking these factors through an FMEA approach based on IT2FS-TOPSIS. Tian et al. [13] proposed an extension of the FMEA method using canonical triangular IT2FS-TODIM (tomada de decisão multicritério) to calculate risk factor weights and to rank risks for electric vehicle charging stations. Aydin et al. [14] extended the FMEA method by integrating the best-worst method (BWM) and picture fuzzy multi-attributive border approximation area comparison (PF-MABAC) to rank fire and explosion risks in the oil and gas industry, demonstrating effective modeling of uncertainties. Zheng et al. [15] proposed an extension of the FMEA method by integrating the heronian mean (HM) operator, which accounts for interdependent relationships among expert evaluations, with interval type-2 fuzzy numbers (IT2FN) and the ORESTE (organisation, rangement et synthèse de données relatives) technique, and applied this approach to a nuclear reheat valve system. In their study, Zhou et al. [16] demonstrated the dynamic evaluation of risks for a motorized spindle using an FMEA method based on interval-valued spherical fuzzy theory, which models decision-makers' hesitancy and uncertainty arising from conflicting information.

In the literature, various types of fuzzy sets, such as fuzzy sets, IT2FS, canonical triangular IT2FS, and picture fuzzy sets, have been employed to extend the FMEA method to model uncertainties in its applications. Fuzzy sets address only uncertainty, while intuitionistic fuzzy sets handle both vagueness and imprecision; however, neither approach provides a solution when experts hesitate to express their membership. The neutrosophic system represents imprecision, ambiguity, and inconsistent uncertainties through three components: truth, indeterminacy, and falsity memberships [17]. Neutrosophic sets are a generalized form of fuzzy sets, intuitionistic fuzzy sets, and interval-valued sets, where the membership degree is defined by three components truth, indeterminacy, and falsity allowing for more flexible modeling of uncertainties [18]. However, as noted by Deli and Subaş [19], to model the complexities and uncertainties in decision-making processes, studies have integrated FMEA with neutrosophic fuzzy set types such as single-valued neutrosophic sets (SVNS) [20], single-valued trapezoidal neutrosophic numbers (SVTNNs) [21], and interval-valued neutrosophic sets (IVNSs) [22].

In this study, unlike the approaches in the literature, the FMEA method based on the PERT distribution, originally proposed by Mutlu and Altuntaş [23], is extended within the neutrosophic set framework. In this study, the FMEA risk parameters severity (S), occurrence (O), and detection (D) are not assumed to have equal weights; instead, their weights are determined using the AHP method based on single-valued neutrosophic sets (SVNS) and triangular fuzzy numbers (TFNs). Furthermore, instead of using classical (crisp) evaluations for these parameters, the neutrosophic framework-based PERT method developed by Romero Fernández et al. [24] is integrated into FMEA, thereby accounting for both uncertainty in the assessments and temporal variability. This integration addresses the limitations of the classical FMEA-PERT method. In the following sections, the neutrosophic set-based AHP and the integration of PERT-FMEA are introduced, the proposed method is demonstrated through a case study, and the results are discussed in the Conclusion section.

2 METHOD AND MATERIALS

In this study, within the scope of Step 1, the NPERT method was integrated into the FMEA framework. In Step 2, the FMEA method was further enhanced through the integration of the NAHP approach. Within Step 3, the outputs from Step 1 and Step 2 were integrated using the risk priority number (RPN) method based on the exponential and weighted geometric mean (EWGM), and the risk levels of the factors were determined accordingly. The applicability of the proposed method has been demonstrated through the analysis and evaluation of occupational safety and operational risks in a centrally controlled natural-gas heating system. The workflow followed in this study is presented in Figure 1.

The following section presents the definitions of neutrosophic sets, single-valued neutrosophic sets (SVNS), and single-valued triangular neutrosophic numbers (SVTNN), along with the definitions of neutrosophic PERT [25], Neutrosophic AHP [26], and their integration with FMEA.

Figure 1: Workflow diagram

2.1 Definition of Neutrosophic Set

Definition 1 [19, 27]: A neutrosophic set N is characterized by three membership functions: a truth membership function $T_{Ne}(x)$, an indeterminacy membership function $I_{Ne}(x)$, and a falsity membership function $F_{Ne}(x)$. Here, $x \in X$, where X is point space. The functions are defined as $T_{Ne}(x): X \rightarrow]0^-, 1^+[$, $I_{Ne}(x): X \rightarrow]0^-, 1^+[$ and $F_{Ne}(x): X \rightarrow]0^-, 1^+[$. Furthermore, there is no restriction on the sum of, $T_{Ne}(x)$, $I_{Ne}(x)$ and $F_{Ne}(x)$, and condition $T_A(x) + I_A(x) + F_A(x) \leq 3^+$ holds.

Definition 2 [19, 27]: A SVN defined on a universal set X is expressed as: $A = \{ \langle x, T_{Ne}(x), I_{Ne}(x), F_{Ne}(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$ where $T_{Ne}(x): X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ denotes the truth membership function, $I_{Ne}(x): X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ denotes the indeterminacy membership function, and $F_{Ne}(x): X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ denotes the falsity membership function. For each $x \in X$, the following condition holds: $0 \leq T_{Ne}(x) + I_{Ne}(x) + F_{Ne}(x) \leq 3$. A single-valued neutrosophic number (SVNN) is denoted as $Ne = (d, e, f)$, where $d, e, f \in [0, 1]$ and the condition $d + e + f \leq 3$ is satisfied.

Definition 3 [19, 27]: A SVTNN is denoted as $\tilde{a} = \langle (a_1, a_2, a_3); \alpha_{\tilde{a}}, \theta_{\tilde{a}}, \beta_{\tilde{a}} \rangle$, and represents a neutrosophic set defined on the set of real numbers R . The truth, indeterminacy, and falsity membership functions of this number are given as follows. Here, $\alpha_{\tilde{a}}, \theta_{\tilde{a}}, \beta_{\tilde{a}} \in [0, 1]$, and $a_1, a_2, a_3 \in R$ such that $a_1 \leq a_2 \leq a_3$.

$$T_{\tilde{a}} = \begin{cases} \alpha_{\tilde{a}} \left(\frac{x - a_1}{a_2 - a_1} \right), & (a_1 \leq x \leq a_2) \\ \alpha_{\tilde{a}}, & x = a_2 \\ \alpha_{\tilde{a}} \left(\frac{a_3 - x}{a_3 - a_2} \right), & a_2 < x \leq a_3 \\ 0, & otherwise \end{cases} \tag{1}$$

$$I_{\tilde{a}} = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{a_2 - x + \theta_{\tilde{a}}(x - a_1)}{a_2 - a_1} \right), & (a_1 \leq x \leq a_2) \\ \theta_{\tilde{a}}, & x = a_2 \\ \left(\frac{x - a_2 + \theta_{\tilde{a}}(a_3 - x)}{a_3 - a_2} \right), & a_2 < x \leq a_3 \\ 1, & otherwise \end{cases} \tag{2}$$

$$F_{\tilde{a}} = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{a_2 - x + \beta_{\tilde{a}}(x - a_1)}{a_2 - a_1} \right), & (a_1 \leq x \leq a_2) \\ \beta_{\tilde{a}}, & x = a_2 \\ \left(\frac{x - a_2 + \beta_{\tilde{a}}(a_3 - x)}{a_3 - a_2} \right), & a_2 < x \leq a_3 \\ 1, & otherwise \end{cases} \tag{3}$$

Definition 4 [19, 27]: Let $\tilde{a} = \langle (a_1, a_2, a_3); \alpha_{\tilde{a}}, \theta_{\tilde{a}}, \beta_{\tilde{a}} \rangle$ and $\tilde{b} = \langle (b_1, b_2, b_3); \alpha_{\tilde{b}}, \theta_{\tilde{b}}, \beta_{\tilde{b}} \rangle$ be two SVTNN, and let $\gamma \neq 0$. Then, the operations between \tilde{a} and \tilde{b} are performed as shown below.

$$\tilde{a} + \tilde{b} = \langle (a_1 + b_1, a_2 + b_2, a_3 + b_3); \alpha_{\tilde{a}} \wedge \alpha_{\tilde{b}}, \theta_{\tilde{a}} \vee \theta_{\tilde{b}}, \beta_{\tilde{a}} \vee \beta_{\tilde{b}} \rangle \tag{4}$$

$$\tilde{a} - \tilde{b} = \langle (a_1 - b_3, a_2 - b_2, a_3 - b_1); \alpha_{\tilde{a}} \wedge \alpha_{\tilde{b}}, \theta_{\tilde{a}} \vee \theta_{\tilde{b}}, \beta_{\tilde{a}} \vee \beta_{\tilde{b}} \rangle \tag{5}$$

$$\tilde{a}^{-1} = \langle \left(\frac{1}{a_3}, \frac{1}{a_2}, \frac{1}{a_1} \right); \alpha_{\tilde{a}}, \theta_{\tilde{a}}, \beta_{\tilde{a}} \rangle \text{ in here, } (\tilde{a} \neq 0) \tag{6}$$

$$\gamma \tilde{a} = \begin{cases} \langle (\gamma a_1, \gamma a_2, \gamma a_3); \alpha_{\tilde{a}}, \theta_{\tilde{a}}, \beta_{\tilde{a}} \rangle & (\gamma > 0) \\ \langle (\gamma b_1, \gamma b_2, \gamma b_3); \alpha_{\tilde{b}}, \theta_{\tilde{b}}, \beta_{\tilde{b}} \rangle & (\gamma < 0) \end{cases} \tag{7}$$

$$\frac{\tilde{a}}{\gamma} = \begin{cases} \langle (\frac{a_1}{\gamma}, \frac{a_2}{\gamma}, \frac{a_3}{\gamma}); \alpha_{\tilde{a}}, \theta_{\tilde{a}}, \beta_{\tilde{a}} \rangle \text{ if } (\gamma > 0) \\ \langle (\frac{a_3}{\gamma}, \frac{a_2}{\gamma}, \frac{a_1}{\gamma}); \alpha_{\tilde{a}}, \theta_{\tilde{a}}, \beta_{\tilde{a}} \rangle \text{ if } (\gamma < 0) \end{cases} \tag{8}$$

$$\frac{\tilde{a}}{b} = \begin{cases} \langle (a_1/b_3, a_2/b_2, a_3/b_1); \alpha_{\tilde{a}} \wedge \alpha_{\tilde{b}}, \theta_{\tilde{a}} \vee \theta_{\tilde{b}}, \beta_{\tilde{a}} \vee \beta_{\tilde{b}} \rangle \text{ if } (a_3 > 0; b_3 > 0) \\ \langle (a_3/b_3, a_2/b_2, a_1/b_1); \alpha_{\tilde{a}} \wedge \alpha_{\tilde{b}}, \theta_{\tilde{a}} \vee \theta_{\tilde{b}}, \beta_{\tilde{a}} \vee \beta_{\tilde{b}} \rangle \text{ if } (a_3 < 0; b_3 > 0) \\ \langle (a_3/b_1, a_2/b_2, a_1/b_3); \alpha_{\tilde{a}} \wedge \alpha_{\tilde{b}}, \theta_{\tilde{a}} \vee \theta_{\tilde{b}}, \beta_{\tilde{a}} \vee \beta_{\tilde{b}} \rangle \text{ if } (a_3 < 0; b_3 < 0) \end{cases} \tag{9}$$

$$\tilde{a}\tilde{b} = \begin{cases} \langle (a_1b_1, a_2b_2, a_3b_3); \alpha_{\tilde{a}} \wedge \alpha_{\tilde{b}}, \theta_{\tilde{a}} \vee \theta_{\tilde{b}}, \beta_{\tilde{a}} \vee \beta_{\tilde{b}} \rangle \text{ if } (a_3 > 0; b_3 > 0) \\ \langle (a_1b_3, a_2b_2, a_3b_1); \alpha_{\tilde{a}} \wedge \alpha_{\tilde{b}}, \theta_{\tilde{a}} \vee \theta_{\tilde{b}}, \beta_{\tilde{a}} \vee \beta_{\tilde{b}} \rangle \text{ if } (a_3 < 0; b_3 > 0) \\ \langle (a_3b_3, a_2b_2, a_1b_1); \alpha_{\tilde{a}} \wedge \alpha_{\tilde{b}}, \theta_{\tilde{a}} \vee \theta_{\tilde{b}}, \beta_{\tilde{a}} \vee \beta_{\tilde{b}} \rangle \text{ if } (a_3 < 0; b_3 < 0) \end{cases} \tag{10}$$

Definition 5 [27, 28]: Let $\tilde{a} = \langle (a_1, a_2, a_3); \alpha_{\tilde{a}}, \theta_{\tilde{a}}, \beta_{\tilde{a}} \rangle$ be a SVTNN. Then, the score function $S(\tilde{a})$, and the accuracy function $A(\tilde{a})$ of a SVTNN are denoted as such and calculated using the formulas given below (see Eq. (11) and (12)).

2.2 Neutrosophic Project Evaluation and Review Techniques (NPERT) in FMEA

Mohamed et al. [27] proposed the neutrosophic project evaluation and review technique (NPERT), which allows for three-point estimation of project completion time within a neutrosophic framework and demonstrated that it provides more accurate results than the classical PERT method. In this study, the NPERT approach is adapted to the FMEA parameters, as in the study by Mutlu and Altuntaş [23]. It is proposed that the severity, occurrence, and detection values used in risk level calculation be modeled using a three-point probability distribution optimistic, pessimistic, and most likely based on the NPERT approach. In evaluating single-valued triangular neutrosophic severity, occurrence, and detection, the linguistic variables and their corresponding triangular fuzzy numbers used by Huang and Zhang [29] (see Table 7) were adopted. Triangular fuzzy numbers are often favored over other fuzzy number types because they are easier to compute [50]. Additionally, the SVNNs in Table 2 were used to assess the decision-maker’s confidence level.

As in the study by Priyadharsini et al. [28], the expected severity, occurrence, and detection values based on the SVTNN using the PERT analysis are presented below, along with definitions 6, 7, 8 and Steps 1.5 and 1.6. The sequential steps followed are presented as follows:

Step 1.1: Determination of the scope for risk analysis.

Step 1.2: Formation of the FMEA team consisting of experts related to the scope of the risk analysis. Let $j = \{1, 2, \dots, m\}$ represent the number of experts.

Step 1.3: Identification of hazards and risks. Let the number of risk factors be $i = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$, and the i th risk factor be denoted as FM_i . The evaluation of the i th risk factor by the j th decision-maker is denoted as FM_i^j .

Step 1.4: Each decision-maker evaluates the severity (S), occurrence (O), and detection (D) of each risk factor FM_i^j using the linguistic variables provided in Table 1, while the confidence level in the given assessment is evaluated using the linguistic variables presented in Table 2.

Table 1 Linguistic scale for severity, occurrence, and detection assessments with corresponding triangular fuzzy numbers (TFNs)

Risk Level	Severity (S)	Occurrence (O)	Detection (D)	TFNs
1	Almost no	Rarely happen	Extremely detectable	(1, 1, 3)
2	Nothing serious	Less happen	Easily detectable	(1, 3, 5)
3	General serious	Happen occasionally	Attention	(3, 5, 7)
4	Serious	Happen very often	Hard to detect	(5, 7, 9)
5	Extremely	Prone to happy	Extremely hard to detect	(7, 9, 9)

Table 1 SVNS with linguistic variables are used to assess decision-maker confidence [30, 31]

Linguistic terms	SVNSs	Linguistic terms	SVNSs
Extremely High (EH)	(1.0,0,0)	Medium Low (ML)	(0.4, 0.65, 0.6)
Very Very High (VVH)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.1)	Low (L)	(0.3, 0.75, 0.7)
Very High (VH)	(0.8, 0.15, 0.2)	Very Low (VL)	(0.2, 0.85, 0.8)
High (H)	(0.7, 0.25, 0.3)	Very Very Low (VLL)	(0.1, 0.9, 0.9)
Medium High (MH)	(0.6, 0.35, 0.4)	Extremely Low (EL)	(0, 1.0, 1.0)
Fit (F)	(0.5, 0.5, 0.5)		

Definition 6 [28]: The single-valued triangular neutrosophic optimistic severity $\tilde{S}_o^{FM_i^j} = \langle (S_{o1_{FM_i^j}}, S_{o2_{FM_i^j}}, S_{o3_{FM_i^j}}); \alpha_o \tilde{s}_{FM_i^j}, \theta_o \tilde{s}_{FM_i^j}, \beta_o \tilde{s}_{FM_i^j} \rangle$ represents the lowest severity level that may be encountered if risk FM_i^j occurs. The optimistic occurrence $\tilde{O}_o^{FM_i^j} = \langle (O_{o1_{FM_i^j}}, O_{o2_{FM_i^j}}, O_{o3_{FM_i^j}}); \alpha_o \tilde{o}_{FM_i^j}, \theta_o \tilde{o}_{FM_i^j}, \beta_o \tilde{o}_{FM_i^j} \rangle$ represents the lowest likelihood of occurrence of risk FM_i^j . The optimistic detection $\tilde{D}_o^{FM_i^j} = \langle (D_{o1_{FM_i^j}}, D_{o2_{FM_i^j}}, D_{o3_{FM_i^j}}); \alpha_o \tilde{d}_{FM_i^j}, \theta_o \tilde{d}_{FM_i^j}, \beta_o \tilde{d}_{FM_i^j} \rangle$ represents the highest level of detection of risk FM_i^j .

Definition 7 [28]: The single-valued triangular neutrosophic pessimistic severity $\tilde{S}_p^{FM_i^j} = \langle (S_{p1_{FM_i^j}}, S_{p2_{FM_i^j}}, S_{p3_{FM_i^j}}); \alpha_p \tilde{s}_{FM_i^j}, \theta_p \tilde{s}_{FM_i^j}, \beta_p \tilde{s}_{FM_i^j} \rangle$ represents the highest severity level that may be encountered if risk FM_i^j occurs. The pessimistic occurrence $\tilde{O}_p^{FM_i^j} = \langle (O_{p1_{FM_i^j}}, O_{p2_{FM_i^j}}, O_{p3_{FM_i^j}}); \alpha_p \tilde{o}_{FM_i^j}, \theta_p \tilde{o}_{FM_i^j}, \beta_p \tilde{o}_{FM_i^j} \rangle$ represents the high likelihood of occurrence of risk FM_i^j . The pessimistic detection $\tilde{D}_p^{FM_i^j} = \langle (D_{p1_{FM_i^j}}, D_{p2_{FM_i^j}}, D_{p3_{FM_i^j}}); \alpha_p \tilde{d}_{FM_i^j}, \theta_p \tilde{d}_{FM_i^j}, \beta_p \tilde{d}_{FM_i^j} \rangle$ represents the lowest level of detection of risk FM_i^j .

Definition 8 [28]: The single-valued triangular neutrosophic most likely severity $\tilde{S}_m^{FM_i^j} = \langle (S_{m1_{FM_i^j}}, S_{m2_{FM_i^j}}, S_{m3_{FM_i^j}}); \alpha_m \tilde{s}_{FM_i^j}, \theta_m \tilde{s}_{FM_i^j}, \beta_m \tilde{s}_{FM_i^j} \rangle$ represents the average severity level that may be encountered if risk FM_i^j occurs. The most likely occurrence $\tilde{O}_m^{FM_i^j} = \langle (O_{m1_{FM_i^j}}, O_{m2_{FM_i^j}}, O_{m3_{FM_i^j}}); \alpha_m \tilde{o}_{FM_i^j}, \theta_m \tilde{o}_{FM_i^j}, \beta_m \tilde{o}_{FM_i^j} \rangle$ represents the average likelihood of occurrence of risk FM_i^j . The most likely detection $\tilde{D}_m^{FM_i^j} = \langle (D_{m1_{FM_i^j}}, D_{m2_{FM_i^j}}, D_{m3_{FM_i^j}}); \alpha_m \tilde{d}_{FM_i^j}, \theta_m \tilde{d}_{FM_i^j}, \beta_m \tilde{d}_{FM_i^j} \rangle$ represents the average level of detection of risk FM_i^j .

Step 1.5 [27, 28]: For risk FM_i^j the score functions of the single-valued triangular neutrosophic optimistic Severity $\tilde{S}_{oFM_i^j}$, pessimistic severity $\tilde{S}_{pFM_i^j}$, and most likely severity $\tilde{S}_{mFM_i^j}$ are given in Eq. (13)–(15), respectively. Similarly, the optimistic occurrence $\tilde{O}_{oFM_i^j}$, pessimistic occurrence $\tilde{O}_{pFM_i^j}$, and most likely occurrence $\tilde{O}_{mFM_i^j}$ are calculated using Eq. (16)–(18), while the optimistic detection $\tilde{D}_{oFM_i^j}$, pessimistic detection $\tilde{D}_{pFM_i^j}$, and most likely detection $\tilde{D}_{mFM_i^j}$ are calculated using Eq. (19)–(22).

Using the single-valued triangular neutrosophic optimistic, pessimistic, and most likely severity, occurrence, and detection values determined for the risk FM_i^j , the expected severity $Se_{FM_i^j}$,

expected occurrence $Oe_{FM_i^j}$, and expected detection $De_{FM_i^j}$ along with their standard deviation values are calculated respectively by Eq. (22), (23), and (24).

$$S(\tilde{S}_{oFM_i^j}) = \frac{1}{8} * \left(S_{o1_{FM_i^j}} + S_{o2_{FM_i^j}} + S_{o3_{FM_i^j}} \right) * (2 + \alpha_o \tilde{s}_{FM_i^j} - \theta_o \tilde{s}_{FM_i^j} - \beta_o \tilde{s}_{FM_i^j}) \tag{13}$$

$$S(\tilde{S}_{pFM_i^j}) = \frac{1}{8} * \left(S_{p1_{FM_i^j}} + S_{p2_{FM_i^j}} + S_{p3_{FM_i^j}} \right) * (2 + \alpha_p \tilde{s}_{FM_i^j} - \theta_p \tilde{s}_{FM_i^j} - \beta_p \tilde{s}_{FM_i^j}) \tag{14}$$

$$S(\tilde{S}_{mFM_i^j}) = \frac{1}{8} * \left(S_{m1_{FM_i^j}} + S_{m2_{FM_i^j}} + S_{m3_{FM_i^j}} \right) * (2 + \alpha_m \tilde{s}_{FM_i^j} - \theta_m \tilde{s}_{FM_i^j} - \beta_m \tilde{s}_{FM_i^j}) \tag{15}$$

$$S(\tilde{O}_{oFM_i^j}) = \frac{1}{8} * \left(O_{o1_{FM_i^j}} + O_{o2_{FM_i^j}} + O_{o3_{FM_i^j}} \right) * (2 + \alpha_o \tilde{o}_{FM_i^j} - \theta_o \tilde{o}_{FM_i^j} - \beta_o \tilde{o}_{FM_i^j}) \tag{16}$$

$$S(\tilde{O}_{pFM_i^j}) = \frac{1}{8} * \left(O_{p1_{FM_i^j}} + O_{p2_{FM_i^j}} + O_{p3_{FM_i^j}} \right) * (2 + \alpha_p \tilde{o}_{FM_i^j} - \theta_p \tilde{o}_{FM_i^j} - \beta_p \tilde{o}_{FM_i^j}) \tag{17}$$

$$S(\tilde{O}_{mFM_i^j}) = \frac{1}{8} * \left(O_{m1_{FM_i^j}} + O_{m2_{FM_i^j}} + O_{m3_{FM_i^j}} \right) * (2 + \alpha_m \tilde{o}_{FM_i^j} - \theta_m \tilde{o}_{FM_i^j} - \beta_m \tilde{o}_{FM_i^j}) \tag{18}$$

$$S(\tilde{D}_{oFM_i^j}) = \frac{1}{8} * \left(D_{o1_{FM_i^j}} + D_{o2_{FM_i^j}} + D_{o3_{FM_i^j}} \right) * (2 + \alpha_o \tilde{d}_{FM_i^j} - \theta_o \tilde{d}_{FM_i^j} - \beta_o \tilde{d}_{FM_i^j}) \tag{19}$$

$$S(\tilde{D}_{pFM_i^j}) = \frac{1}{8} * \left(D_{p1_{FM_i^j}} + D_{p2_{FM_i^j}} + D_{p3_{FM_i^j}} \right) * (2 + \alpha_p \tilde{d}_{FM_i^j} - \theta_p \tilde{d}_{FM_i^j} - \beta_p \tilde{d}_{FM_i^j}) \tag{20}$$

$$S(\tilde{D}_{mFM_i^j}) = \frac{1}{8} * \left(D_{m1_{FM_i^j}} + D_{m2_{FM_i^j}} + D_{m3_{FM_i^j}} \right) * (2 + \alpha_m \tilde{d}_{FM_i^j} - \theta_m \tilde{d}_{FM_i^j} - \beta_m \tilde{d}_{FM_i^j}) \tag{21}$$

Step 1.6: Let $Se_{FM_i^j}$ denote the expected severity value for the risk FM_i^j . Assuming there are five experts, the expected severity value for FM_1 based on the decision-makers' evaluations is calculated as the arithmetic mean: $Se_{FM_1} = \frac{Se_{FM_1^1} + Se_{FM_1^2} + Se_{FM_1^3} + Se_{FM_1^4} + Se_{FM_1^5}}{5}$.

2.3 Neutrosophic AHP in FMEA

The AHP, developed by Saaty [32], is employed to determine the relative importance weights of the FMEA parameters: severity, occurrence, and detection. To model uncertainties in the application of the AHP method and obtain more accurate analysis results, various studies have extended the method using different types of fuzzy logic, including fuzzy [33], fuzzy type-2 [34], intuitionistic fuzzy [35, 36], pythagorean fuzzy [37], spherical fuzzy [38], and neutrosophic fuzzy [27]. Among these, the Neutrosophic AHP (NAHP) method was first integrated into the FMEA approach by Yucesan and Gul [26], who demonstrated its effectiveness. The five steps followed in the NAHP process are outlined below in sequence [26].

Step 2.1: In the context of risk analysis and evaluation, alternatives, criteria, and sub-criteria are identified, and the hierarchical structure is constructed.

Step 2.2: For the criteria whose relative importance weights are to be determined, the decision-makers identified in Step 1.2 perform pairwise comparisons, resulting in a pairwise comparison matrix. The relative importance of the criteria is evaluated using the linguistic variables in Table 3, while the decision-makers' confidence levels are assessed using the linguistic variables in Table 2. The neutrosophic decision matrix is presented in Eq. (25).

$$\tilde{d}_{kl} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \dots & \tilde{d}_{1m} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \tilde{d}_{m1} & \dots & 1 \end{bmatrix} \text{ where } \tilde{d}_{kl} = \tilde{d}_{lk}^{-1} \tag{25}$$

Table 3 Linguistic variables and TFNs used to evaluate risk factor importance weights [39, 40]

Linguistic scale	TFNs	Reciprocal TFNs
Equally Important (EI)	(1, 1, 1)	(1, 1, 1)
Weakly More Important (WMI)	(1/2, 1, 3/2)	(2/3, 1, 2)
Strong More Important (SMI)	(3/2, 2, 5/2)	(2/5, 1/2, 2/3)
Very Strong More Important (VSMI)	(5/2, 3, 7/2)	(2/7, 1/3, 2/5)
Absolute More Important (AMI)	(7/2, 4, 9/2)	(2/9, 1/4, 2/7)

Step 2.3 [26, 27]: The neutrosophic decision matrix is used to determine criteria weights and is converted into a deterministic decision matrix using Eq. (11). Subsequently, the classical AHP steps are applied using the deterministic decision matrix.

Step 2.4 [26, 27]: In the classical AHP method, expert judgment consistency is evaluated using the consistency ratio (CR). A CR value below 0.1 indicates that the expert evaluations are consistent.

Step 2.4.1: The deterministic pairwise comparison matrix is multiplied by the relative importance weight vector.

Step 2.4.2: Each element in the weighted sum vector is divided by the corresponding priority value.

Step 2.4.3: The average of the values obtained from Step 1.4.2 is calculated to determine λ_{max} .

Step 2.4.4: The consistency index (CI) is calculated using λ_{max} and the number of criteria, n , as follows: $CI = \frac{\lambda_{max} - n}{n - 1}$.

Step 2.4.5: The consistency ratio (CR) is calculated using the consistency index (CI) and the randomly generated index (RI) as follows: $CR = \frac{CI}{RI}$.

Step 2.5 [26, 27]: The final ranking is obtained by considering the final weight of each criterion.

2.4 Integration on NAHP, NPERT with FMEA

In the FMEA method, severity (S), occurrence (O), and detection (D) values are multiplied according to the classical risk priority number (RPN) formula for ranking failure modes. The accuracy of this formula in representing real situations has been widely debated in the literature, prompting the development of new methods. Among the main proposals for ranking failure modes are the fuzzy RPN based on the fuzzy weighted geometric mean [41, 42], the RPN based on the EWGM [43], and the RPN based on fuzzy rule-based systems and grey relational analysis [44]. In this study, within the scope of Steps 1.5–1.6, the values of Se_{FM_i} , Oe_{FM_i} and De_{FM_i} are calculated for each risk factor FM_i using NPERT. In Step 2.5, the weights w_S , w_O and w_D for severity (S), occurrence (O), and detection (D) are determined using NAHP analysis. The calculation of the risk priority number for each risk factor FM_i and the related explanations of risk levels are presented in Steps 3.1 and 3.2.

Step 3.1 [43, 45]: To calculate the RPN, this study considers the exponential and weighted geometric mean method (EWGM) proposed by Al Mashaqbeh et al. [43], which facilitates the weighted aggregation of expert opinions in uncertain environments. For each risk factor FM_i , the RPN based on EWGM, denoted as $EWGM_{RPN_i}$ is calculated using Eq. (26).

Step 3.2 [43, 45]: The $EWGM_{RPN_i}$ values are ranked in descending order. The highest $EWGM_{RPN_i}$ value is assigned the lowest risk rank, and the risk levels of the risk factors are determined accordingly.

3 CASE STUDY

Detecting potential nonconformities in advance and developing preventive measures during the transportation of natural gas to work and living areas in a centralized natural gas heating system is crucial [46, 47]. Panchal and Srivastava [48] assessed risks in a compressed natural gas distribution system using fuzzy FMEA and grey relational analysis (GRA). Mete [6] identified safety risks in natural gas pipeline transportation by integrating pythagorean fuzzy logic-based FMEA with the AHP-MOORA approach. Jin et al. [49] assessed the risks associated with liquefied natural gas (LNG) carriers using the group FMEA technique. The literature indicates that FMEA-based risk assessment studies on natural gas heating systems are limited. In this study, within Step 1.1, the scope of the risk analysis is defined as the centralized natural gas heating system. The system comprises natural gas boilers, carrier pipes, burners, circulation pumps, expansion tanks, automatic control equipment, and intermediate components. The hot water produced by this system is used to heat campus buildings (administrative building, dormitories, workshops, and guesthouse) and fulfill their hot water needs. Delivered into the boiler from the main supply line with the help of a burner, it is ignited using a 91% air mixture. The water heated inside the boiler, reaching a pressure of 4 bar, is then sent to the heat exchanger. The network water is heated to 45°C and then sent to the accumulation tank and circulation pumps. Hot water leaving the circulation pumps at 60°C is delivered to the radiators of the campus buildings, while water leaving the accumulation tank at 40–45°C is directed to the fixtures for domestic hot water use. The return water temperature in the system drops to 30–35°C, after which it is reheated in the boiler and continues its circulation. In Step 1.2, a team of five experienced experts was formed to conduct the risk assessment, and the members are listed in Table 4. The components of the system are listed in Table 5. The natural gas material flow diagram is shown in Figure 2, and the hot water material flow diagram is shown in Figure 3. The FMEA team performed hazard analysis and risk assessment by considering the relevant flow diagrams.

Figure 2: Natural gas material flow diagram

Figure 3: Hot water material flow diagram

Table 4 FMEA team (decision-makers, roles, professional experiences)

Expert, E_j	Professional	Task	Experience (Years)
E_1	Mechanical Senior Engineer	Unit Manager / Control Engineer	20
E_2	Plumber	Natural Gas Installation Maintenance and Repair	5
E_3	Heating Technician-1	Maintenance and Repair	25
E_4	Heating Technician-2	Maintenance and Repair	25
E_5	Heating Technician-3	Maintenance and Repair	15

Table 5 Natural gas and hot water systems components

No	Component name	No	Component name	No	Component name
1	Main Supply Line	19	Exhaust Flue (Smoke)	37	Ball Valve
2	Gas Transmission Line	20	Chimney	38	Heat Exchanger
3	Ball Valve	21	Balance Tank	39	Ball Valve
4	Thermometer	22	Supply Manifold	40	Thermometer
5	Pump	23	Ball Valve	41	Pressure Gauge
6	Pressure Gauge	24	Circulation Pump	42	Ball Valve
7	Gas Safety Solenoid Valve	25	Ball Valve	43	Accumulation Tank
8	Burner	26	Radiators	44	Ball Valve
9	Boiler	27	Heating System Return Manifold	45	Hot Water Usage Areas
10	Exhaust Flue (Smoke)	28	Expansion Tank	46	Pump
11	Chimney	29	Ball Valve	47	Ball Valve
12	Ball Valve	30	Pump	48	Ball Valve
13	Thermometer	31	Ball Valve	49	Pump
14	Pump	32	Ball Valve	50	Network Water Line
15	Pressure Gauge	33	Duplex Pumps	51	Network Water Valve
16	Gas Safety Solenoid Valve	34	Ball Valve	52	Ball Valve
17	Burner	35	Thermometer	53	Hot Water Return Manifold
18	Boiler	36	Pressure Gauge		

As part of Step 1.3, hazards and risks were identified by the FMEA team and are presented in Table 6. The analysis was carried out using the classical FMEA method, with the support of the S, O, and D evaluation tables referenced by experts in the study of Mutlu and Altuntas [23].

Starting from Step 1.4, the analyses were conducted hypothetically. The NPERT-FMEA analysis was performed for each risk factor defined in Table 6, based on evaluations by five experts. The assessments for FM_1 are presented in Table 7.

Within the scope of Step 1.5, the hypothetical evaluations made by five experts in Step 1.4 for the S, O, and D parameters of $FM_1 - FM_{20}$, using Table 1 and Table 2, were converted into crisp values using the score functions provided in Eq. (13) – (21), and the results are presented in Table 8 and 9.

Within the scope of Step 1.6, the arithmetic mean of the S, O, and D parameter evaluations obtained from five experts for $FM_1 - FM_{20}$ in Step 1.5 was calculated, and the average values of S, O, and D were presented in Table 14. For FM_1 , the average S value is determined as: $Se_{FM_1} =$

$$\frac{Se_{FM_1} + Se_{FM_{12}} + Se_{FM_{13}} + Se_{FM_{14}} + Se_{FM_{15}}}{5} = \frac{4.55 + 6.98 + 4.82 + 5.42 + 5.08}{5} = 5.37.$$

Table 6 Identified failure modes and risks for the central natural gas heating system

FM_i	Failure Mode	Risk
FM ₁	Loss of installation water	Boiler explosion due to increased pressure
FM ₂	Overheating of thermostat water	Explosion of the natural gas boiler
FM ₃	Deformation of electrical cables	System fire due to short circuit
FM ₄	Failure of the expansion tank	Water leakage and pipe rupture/explosion due to inability to discharge excess water and pressure
FM ₅	Malfunction of the pressure gauge in the hot water boiler	Decrease in comfort conditions due to reduced water in the boiler
FM ₆	Overheating of the boiler power control panel	Financial loss due to the burning of the panel and all connected components
FM ₇	Gas leakage from the natural gas supply line	Explosion caused by gas accumulation in the absence of a gas detection sensor and automatic shutoff system
FM ₈	Overheating of thermostat water	Pipe blockage due to scale and sediment build-up, and reduced heat transfer efficiency
FM ₉	Malfunction of the pressure gauge in the hot water boiler	Cracking of the heat exchanger and circulation blockage due to sudden temperature rise and sediment accumulation
FM ₁₀	Malfunction of the pressure gauge in the hot water boiler	Decreased operational efficiency due to air accumulation in the radiator
FM ₁₁	Overheating of thermostat water	Financial loss due to heat leakage at radiator connection points
FM ₁₂	Overheating of thermostat water	Pipe deformation and surface cracks due to excessive temperature
FM ₁₃	Loss of installation water	Reduction in thermal comfort conditions
FM ₁₄	Power outage	System failure due to inability to circulate water to radiators
FM ₁₅	High voltage in the boiler power control panel	Fire in the electrical panel
FM ₁₆	Main shut-off valve malfunction	Gas accumulation due to failure to cut off the gas during another malfunction, leading to increased temperature and pressure
FM ₁₇	High voltage in the boiler power control panel	Burning of contactors and fuses
FM ₁₈	Faulty complete closure of valves	Severe burns due to sudden discharge of hot water during maintenance
FM ₁₉	Worn pipe flange gaskets	Water leakage from pipes connected to flanges
FM ₂₀	Circulation pump failure	Decrease in comfort conditions in hot water usage areas

Table 7 NPERT-FMEA analysis of the S, O, and D parameters for FM₁ in the central natural gas-fired heating system

Severity (S)			
FM_i^j	Optimistic ($S_{o1_{FM_i^j}}, S_{o2_{FM_i^j}}, S_{o3_{FM_i^j}}$); ($\alpha_{oS_{FM_i^j}}, \theta_{oS_{FM_i^j}}, \beta_{oS_{FM_i^j}}$)	Most Likely ($S_{m1_{FM_i^j}}, S_{m2_{FM_i^j}}, S_{m3_{FM_i^j}}$); ($\alpha_{mS_{FM_i^j}}, \theta_{mS_{FM_i^j}}, \beta_{mS_{FM_i^j}}$)	Pessimistic ($S_{p1_{FM_i^j}}, S_{p2_{FM_i^j}}, S_{p3_{FM_i^j}}$); ($\alpha_{pS_{FM_i^j}}, \theta_{pS_{FM_i^j}}, \beta_{pS_{FM_i^j}}$)
FM_1^1	(1, 3, 5); (0.8, 0.15, 0.2)	(3, 5, 7); (0.7, 0.25, 0.3)	(7, 9, 9); (0.9, 0.1, 0.1)
FM_1^2	(3, 5, 7); (0.7, 0.25, 0.3)	(5, 7, 9); (0.8, 0.15, 0.2)	(7, 9, 9); (1, 0, 0)
FM_1^3	(1, 1, 3); (0.6, 0.35, 0.4)	(3, 5, 7); (0.8, 0.15, 0.2)	(7, 9, 9); (1, 0, 0)
FM_1^4	(1, 1, 3); (0.8, 0.15, 0.2)	(5, 7, 9); (0.7, 0.25, 0.3)	(7, 9, 9); (0.9, 0.1, 0.1)
FM_1^5	(1, 3, 5); (0.8, 0.15, 0.2)	(3, 5, 7); (0.8, 0.15, 0.2)	(7, 9, 9); (1, 0, 0)
Occurrence (O)			
FM_i^j	Optimistic ($O_{o1_{FM_i^j}}, O_{o2_{FM_i^j}}, O_{o3_{FM_i^j}}$); ($\alpha_{oO_{FM_i^j}}, \theta_{oO_{FM_i^j}}, \beta_{oO_{FM_i^j}}$)	Most Likely ($O_{m1_{FM_i^j}}, O_{m2_{FM_i^j}}, O_{m3_{FM_i^j}}$); ($\alpha_{mO_{FM_i^j}}, \theta_{mO_{FM_i^j}}, \beta_{mO_{FM_i^j}}$)	Pessimistic ($O_{p1_{FM_i^j}}, O_{p2_{FM_i^j}}, O_{p3_{FM_i^j}}$); ($\alpha_{pO_{FM_i^j}}, \theta_{pO_{FM_i^j}}, \beta_{pO_{FM_i^j}}$)
FM_1^1	(3, 5, 7); (1, 0, 0)	(5, 7, 9); (0.9, 0.1, 0.1)	(7, 9, 9); (1, 0, 0)
FM_1^2	(1, 1, 3); (0.9, 0.1, 0.1)	(1, 3, 5); (0.7, 0.25, 0.3)	(5, 7, 9); (1, 0, 0)
FM_1^3	(1, 1, 3); (0.7, 0.25, 0.3)	(1, 3, 5); (0.9, 0.1, 0.1)	(5, 7, 9); (0.9, 0.1, 0.1)
FM_1^4	(1, 1, 3); (1, 0, 0)	(1, 3, 5); (0.8, 0.15, 0.2)	(7, 9, 9); (1, 0, 0)
FM_1^5	(1, 1, 3); (0.8, 0.15, 0.2)	(3, 5, 7); (0.8, 0.15, 0.2)	(7, 9, 9); (0.9, 0.1, 0.1)
Detection (D)			
FM_i^j	Optimistic ($D_{o1_{FM_i^j}}, D_{o2_{FM_i^j}}, D_{o3_{FM_i^j}}$); ($\alpha_{oD_{FM_i^j}}, \theta_{oD_{FM_i^j}}, \beta_{oD_{FM_i^j}}$)	Most Likely ($D_{m1_{FM_i^j}}, D_{m2_{FM_i^j}}, D_{m3_{FM_i^j}}$); ($\alpha_{mD_{FM_i^j}}, \theta_{mD_{FM_i^j}}, \beta_{mD_{FM_i^j}}$)	Pessimistic ($D_{p1_{FM_i^j}}, D_{p2_{FM_i^j}}, D_{p3_{FM_i^j}}$); ($\alpha_{pD_{FM_i^j}}, \theta_{pD_{FM_i^j}}, \beta_{pD_{FM_i^j}}$)
FM_1^1	(1, 1, 3); (1, 0, 0)	(1, 3, 5); (0.8, 0.15, 0.2)	(5, 7, 9); (0.9, 0.1, 0.1)
FM_1^2	(1, 1, 3); (1, 0, 0)	(3, 5, 7); (0.8, 0.15, 0.2)	(5, 7, 9); (0.9, 0.1, 0.1)
FM_1^3	(1, 1, 3); (0.9, 0.1, 0.1)	(3, 5, 7); (0.7, 0.25, 0.3)	(7, 9, 9); (1, 0, 0)
FM_1^4	(1, 1, 3); (0.7, 0.25, 0.3)	(3, 5, 7); (0.8, 0.15, 0.2)	(7, 9, 9); (0.9, 0.1, 0.1)
FM_1^5	(1, 1, 3); (1, 0, 0)	(3, 5, 7); (0.8, 0.15, 0.2)	(7, 9, 9); (0.8, 0.15, 0.2)

Table 8 The Se_{FM_i} , Oe_{FM_i} , De_{FM_i} score values for FM₁ - FM₂₀ in the central natural gas heating system

FM_i^j	Se_{FM_i}	Oe_{FM_i}	De_{FM_i}	FM_i^j	Se_{FM_i}	Oe_{FM_i}	De_{FM_i}
FM_1^1	4.55	7.47	3.33	FM_5^1	6.19	5.63	4.86
FM_1^2	6.98	3.33	4.56	FM_5^2	6.85	5.16	3.96
FM_1^3	4.82	3.71	4.28	FM_5^3	6.85	5.16	3.96
FM_1^4	5.42	3.86	4.47	FM_5^4	6.19	5.63	4.86
FM_1^5	5.08	5.23	4.65	FM_5^5	6.85	5.16	3.96
FM_2^1	6.25	4.54	2.28	FM_6^1	5.03	3.39	4.54
FM_2^2	6.98	6.92	4.54	FM_6^2	7.75	3.30	2.88
FM_2^3	6.85	8.13	6.35	FM_6^3	6.16	3.58	2.87
FM_2^4	5.39	3.09	2.69	FM_6^4	5.03	3.39	4.54
FM_2^5	7.22	6.92	4.73	FM_6^5	4.13	3.71	3.15
FM_3^1	4.63	5.87	3.13	FM_7^1	5.40	3.39	3.30
FM_3^2	7.13	6.48	2.89	FM_7^2	4.87	4.02	3.96
FM_3^3	7.13	6.48	2.89	FM_7^3	4.87	4.02	3.96
FM_3^4	4.97	6.00	2.59	FM_7^4	6.54	5.76	5.20
FM_3^5	6.79	5.49	3.35	FM_7^5	3.50	6.64	6.07
FM_4^1	5.17	7.68	3.52	FM_8^1	5.03	7.97	2.82
FM_4^2	5.16	6.77	3.81	FM_8^2	6.34	7.84	4.22
FM_4^3	5.16	6.77	3.81	FM_8^3	6.34	7.84	4.22
FM_4^4	5.17	7.68	3.52	FM_8^4	3.53	6.09	3.34
FM_4^5	5.06	7.47	4.45	FM_8^5	6.34	7.84	4.22

Table 9 The Se_{FM_i} , Oe_{FM_i} , De_{FM_i} score values for $FM_1 - FM_{20}$ in the central natural gas heating system (continue)

FM_i^j	Se_{FM_i}	Oe_{FM_i}	De_{FM_i}	FM_i^j	Se_{FM_i}	Oe_{FM_i}	De_{FM_i}
FM_9^1	4.46	5.76	3.10	FM_{15}^1	6.69	3.38	3.18
FM_9^2	7.00	5.40	6.46	FM_{15}^2	6.85	7.47	2.96
FM_9^3	7.00	5.40	6.46	FM_{15}^3	4.36	6.11	4.57
FM_9^4	4.78	5.16	4.73	FM_{15}^4	5.54	7.47	4.53
FM_9^5	7.07	7.31	7.13	FM_{15}^5	6.98	5.78	3.61
FM_{10}^1	4.70	5.63	3.18	FM_{16}^1	5.13	2.48	2.69
FM_{10}^2	5.28	7.03	2.93	FM_{16}^2	7.05	8.13	3.26
FM_{10}^3	5.28	7.03	2.93	FM_{16}^3	7.05	8.13	3.26
FM_{10}^4	3.27	5.00	4.60	FM_{16}^4	6.57	3.37	4.21
FM_{10}^5	6.57	7.31	3.53	FM_{16}^5	7.66	8.13	4.45
FM_{11}^1	7.14	5.29	2.50	FM_{17}^1	5.02	2.97	2.69
FM_{11}^2	7.75	5.29	4.18	FM_{17}^2	6.61	5.18	3.01
FM_{11}^3	7.75	5.29	4.18	FM_{17}^3	6.99	6.87	2.97
FM_{11}^4	5.91	5.29	3.10	FM_{17}^4	5.02	2.97	2.69
FM_{11}^5	6.63	5.63	6.28	FM_{17}^5	6.51	7.84	3.41
FM_{12}^1	5.33	5.63	3.33	FM_{18}^1	3.18	4.77	3.01
FM_{12}^2	6.90	4.90	4.36	FM_{18}^2	3.20	2.31	3.88
FM_{12}^3	6.64	5.30	4.83	FM_{18}^3	5.07	3.70	3.00
FM_{12}^4	5.28	5.49	4.88	FM_{18}^4	4.95	4.88	4.63
FM_{12}^5	6.90	4.90	4.36	FM_{18}^5	3.30	3.06	4.62
FM_{13}^1	4.43	5.53	2.60	FM_{19}^1	2.95	3.58	2.60
FM_{13}^2	3.06	3.47	3.50	FM_{19}^2	4.51	4.54	1.94
FM_{13}^3	3.43	5.63	3.15	FM_{19}^3	5.57	4.01	2.70
FM_{13}^4	5.72	3.61	4.07	FM_{19}^4	2.83	3.75	2.92
FM_{13}^5	4.96	5.49	5.84	FM_{19}^5	6.13	4.92	3.74
FM_{14}^1	5.28	3.88	3.81	FM_{20}^1	2.60	3.06	2.17
FM_{14}^2	5.15	6.48	2.22	FM_{20}^2	2.88	3.20	2.86
FM_{14}^3	5.84	5.67	2.35	FM_{20}^3	4.42	5.29	4.41
FM_{14}^4	5.33	3.66	4.01	FM_{20}^4	3.81	3.71	2.61
FM_{14}^5	7.13	5.10	3.49	FM_{20}^5	4.87	3.37	3.71

3.1 Determination of FMEA Parameter Weights Using NAHP

In this study, the NAHP application steps outlined by Yucesan and Gul [26] were followed to determine the weights of the FMEA parameters. In the NAHP application, to create a more practical and flexible evaluation process for decision-makers, linguistic variables expressed on a 5-grade scale proposed by Srichetta and Thurachon [39] and used in the study by Stanković et al. [40], along with their corresponding triangular fuzzy numbers (TFNs) (see Table 3), were employed. Additionally, the confidence level of decision-makers in their judgments was considered using single valued neutrosophic sets (SVNS) truth, indeterminacy, and falsity memberships expressed on an 11-grade scale, as proposed by Şahin and Yiğider [30] and applied in the study by Hsiung et al. [31] (see Table 2).

Within Step 2.1, the hierarchical structure to be evaluated using the group decision-making technique with NAHP in this study is presented in Figure 4.

Within Step 2.2, evaluations collected through pairwise comparisons by five hypothetical decision-makers are presented in Table 10. In Step 2.3, the evaluations in the decision matrix are converted into crisp values using Eq. (22), (23), and (24) (see Table 11). The arithmetic mean of the decision-makers' evaluations is then calculated to obtain the group decision matrix (see Table 12). This matrix is subsequently normalized, and the eigenvector and parameter weights are derived (see Table 13).

Figure 4: Hierarchical structure for FMEA criteria

Table 10 Neutrosophic pairwise comparison matrix for risk parameters

Risk Parameter	Expert, E_j	S	O	D
S	E_1	(1, 1, 1); (1, 0, 0)	(3/2, 2, 5/2); (0.8, 0.15, 0.2)	(5/2, 3, 7/2); (0.7, 0.25, 0.3)
	E_2	(1, 1, 1); (1, 0, 0)	(3/2, 2, 5/2); (0.9, 0.1, 0.1)	(2/3, 1, 2); (0.9, 0.1, 0.1)
	E_3	(1, 1, 1); (1, 0, 0)	(3/2, 2, 5/2); (0.6, 0.35, 0.4)	(5/2, 3, 7/2); (0.8, 0.15, 0.2)
	E_4	(1, 1, 1); (1, 0, 0)	(2/5, 1/2, 2/3); (0.8, 0.15, 0.2)	(5/2, 3, 7/2); (0.8, 0.15, 0.2)
	E_5	(1, 1, 1); (1, 0, 0)	(5/2, 3, 7/2); (0.6, 0.35, 0.4)	(5/2, 3, 7/2); (0.8, 0.15, 0.2)
O	E_1	(2/5, 1/2, 2/3); (0.8, 0.15, 0.2)	(1, 1, 1); (1, 0, 0)	(2/3, 1, 2); (0.6, 0.35, 0.4)
	E_2	(2/5, 1/2, 2/3); (0.9, 0.1, 0.1)	(1, 1, 1); (1, 0, 0)	(1/2, 1, 3/2); (0.6, 0.35, 0.4)
	E_3	(2/5, 1/2, 2/3); (0.6, 0.35, 0.4)	(1, 1, 1); (1, 0, 0)	(2/5, 1/2, 2/3); (0.7, 0.25, 0.3)
	E_4	(3/2, 2, 5/2); (0.8, 0.15, 0.2)	(1, 1, 1); (1, 0, 0)	(2/5, 1/2, 2/3); (0.7, 0.25, 0.3)
	E_5	(2/7, 1/3, 2/5); (0.6, 0.35, 0.4)	(1, 1, 1); (1, 0, 0)	(2/5, 1/2, 2/3); (0.8, 0.15, 0.2)
D	E_1	(2/7, 1/3, 2/5); (0.7, 0.25, 0.3)	(1/2, 1, 3/2); (0.6, 0.35, 0.4)	(1, 1, 1); (1, 0, 0)
	E_2	(1/2, 1, 3/2); (0.9, 0.1, 0.1)	(2/3, 1, 2); (0.6, 0.35, 0.4)	(1, 1, 1); (1, 0, 0)
	E_3	(2/5, 1/2, 2/3); (0.8, 0.15, 0.2)	(2/7, 1/3, 2/5); (0.8, 0.15, 0.2)	(1, 1, 1); (1, 0, 0)
	E_4	(2/7, 1/3, 2/5); (0.8, 0.15, 0.2)	(3/2, 2, 5/2); (0.7, 0.25, 0.3)	(1, 1, 1); (1, 0, 0)
	E_5	(2/7, 1/3, 2/5); (0.8, 0.15, 0.2)	(3/2, 2, 5/2); (0.8, 0.15, 0.2)	(1, 1, 1); (1, 0, 0)

Table 11 Deterministic decision matrix for the risk parameters

Risk Parameter	Expert, E_j	S	O	D
S	E_1	1.125	1.838	2.419
	E_2	1.125	2.025	1.238
	E_3	1.125	1.388	2.756
	E_4	1.125	0.480	2.756
	E_5	1.125	2.081	2.756
O	E_1	0.480	1.125	0.848
	E_2	0.529	1.125	0.694
	E_3	0.362	1.125	0.421
	E_4	1.838	1.125	0.421
	E_5	0.236	1.125	0.480
D	E_1	0.274	0.694	1.125
	E_2	1.013	0.848	1.125
	E_3	0.480	0.312	1.125
	E_4	0.312	1.613	1.125
	E_5	0.312	1.838	1.125

As indicated in Step 2.4.3, the values given in Table 14 are obtained, and the value of λ_{max} is calculated as $(\frac{3.127+3.105+3.079}{3}) = 3.104$. The number of criteria compared is 3, corresponding to an RI value of 0.580 [9]. Within the scope of Step 2.4.4, the CI value was calculated as 0.052. In Step 2.4.5, the CR value was determined to be 0.089. Since the CR value is less than 0.1, the evaluations of the decision-maker are considered consistent [32]. The weights of S, O, and D will be considered respectively as $w_{S_e} = 0.497$, $w_{O_e} = 0.247$, and $w_{D_e} = 0.256$.

Table 12 Group decision matrix

	<i>S</i>	<i>O</i>	<i>D</i>
<i>S</i>	1.125	1.562	2.385
<i>O</i>	0.689	1.125	0.573
<i>D</i>	0.478	1.061	1.125
Total of the column	2.292	3.748	4.083

Table 13 Normalized matrix, risk parameter eigenvectors, and their weights

	<i>S</i>	<i>O</i>	<i>D</i>	Eigenvector	Weight
<i>S</i>	0.491	0.417	0.584	1.492	0.497
<i>O</i>	0.301	0.300	0.140	0.741	0.247
<i>D</i>	0.209	0.283	0.276	0.767	0.256

Table 14 Vectors used for the calculation λ_{max}

Vector-1	1.555	0.767	0.787
Vector-2	3.127	3.105	3.079

In Step 1.7, the values obtained from Step 1.6 were used to calculate the expected risk priority number using Eq. (25), and the results are presented in Table 15. For FM₁, the value of EWGM_{RPN₁} is calculated as $3^{(5.37)*0.497} * 3^{(4.72)*0.247} * 3^{(4.26)*0.256} = 223.45$. The EWGM_{RPN_i} values and their corresponding rankings for the the 20 identified risk factors are presented in Table 15.

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Table 15 Average S, O, and D values for FM₁ - FM₂₀ in the central gas heating system

<i>FM_i</i>	Classic FMEA					NAHP-NPERT-FMEA				
	<i>S</i>	<i>O</i>	<i>D</i>	RPN	Rank	<i>Se_{FM_i}</i>	<i>Oe_{FM_i}</i>	<i>De_{FM_i}</i>	EWGM _{RPN_i}	Rank
FM ₁	10	9	1	90	1	5,37	4,72	4,26	223,45	13
FM ₂	10	8	1	80	2	6,54	5,92	4,12	562,96	3
FM ₃	10	5	1	50	3	6,13	6,06	2,97	339,91	10
FM ₄	6	8	1	48	4	5,14	7,27	3,82	349,39	9
FM ₅	8	5	1	40	5	6,59	5,35	4,32	524,10	5
FM ₆	10	2	2	40	5	5,62	3,47	3,59	151,55	16
FM ₇	10	2	2	40	5	5,04	4,76	4,50	201,70	15
FM ₈	6	6	1	36	6	5,52	7,52	3,76	451,16	6
FM ₉	8	4	1	32	7	6,06	5,81	5,58	635,92	1
FM ₁₀	6	5	1	30	8	5,02	6,40	3,43	231,38	12
FM ₁₁	7	4	1	28	9	7,04	5,36	4,05	622,99	2
FM ₁₂	5	5	1	25	10	6,21	5,25	4,35	418,76	7
FM ₁₃	3	6	1	18	11	4,32	4,75	3,83	112,85	17
FM ₁₄	6	3	1	18	11	5,75	4,96	3,18	216,28	14
FM ₁₅	10	1	1	10	12	6,08	6,04	3,77	411,53	8
FM ₁₆	10	1	1	10	12	6,69	6,05	3,57	544,49	4
FM ₁₇	5	1	1	5	13	6,03	5,17	2,95	250,56	11
FM ₁₈	2	2	1	4	14	3,94	3,74	3,83	69,57	19
FM ₁₉	2	2	1	4	14	4,40	4,16	2,78	74,53	18
FM ₂₀	1	1	1	1	15	3,72	3,73	3,15	50,72	20

Figure 5: The proposed method and the classic FMEA method

4 CONCLUSION

In this study, the FMEA method parameters' weights were determined using the NAHP approach, and the evaluation of risk factors was conducted for the first time using the NPERT method. Additionally, RPN calculation was based on EWGM, and an integrated risk analysis and assessment method was proposed to ensure information flow among these approaches. The applicability of the proposed method was demonstrated on a central natural gas heating system. A real-world application was performed using the classic FMEA method to evaluate 20 risk factors identified by the FMEA team for this system. In the classical FMEA method, the risk criteria are typically assumed to have equal weights. In contrast, our study proposes a method in which risk parameter weights are determined based on expert judgment. The application of the proposed method was conducted hypothetically, with risk parameter weights determined as $w_S = 0.497$, $w_O = 0.247$, and $w_D = 0.256$, respectively.

While 15 different risk levels were obtained for 20 distinct risks using the classical FMEA method, the proposed method produced 20 severity, 20 occurrence, and 19 detection values, resulting in 20 distinct Risk Priority Numbers (see Figure 5). The proposed method addresses the similar risk ranking problem caused by the difficulty of evaluating risk factors with crisp values, uncertainties arising from differences in decision-makers' knowledge levels, and the assumption of equal weights for risk factors. Furthermore, it overcomes the issue of similar RPN values resulting from limitations in the traditional Risk Priority Number (RPN) formula when combining S, O, and D.

The methodology introduced in this study is effective for addressing prioritization or selection problems and offers tangible benefits. Additionally, the proposed framework shows potential for application in risk assessment across various fields, such as construction and healthcare. Future studies should focus on collecting empirical data to validate these findings. Furthermore, the stability of the priority ranking obtained using the proposed approach can be evaluated. To achieve this, alternative priority rankings can be generated using criterion weights from previous studies, and their consistency can be assessed using correlation analysis.

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